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Single-grain Re-engineered Nd-Fe-B Permanent Magnets

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GREENE IN A NUTSHELL

Main goal: **Tackling the environmental and supply challenges** associated with permanent magnets as **crucial components** of many products that power a green energy future, e.g. wind turbines and electric vehicles

How: **Pioneering advancements in high-performance permanent magnets**, by re-engineering their microstructure to make them more powerful while at the same time reducing rare earths content as critical / strategic materials

8

Million EUR
Funding

15

Partners from
10 European
Countries

4

Years
June 2024 –
May 2028

PROJECT GOALS

Resource efficient, high-performance Nd-Fe-B magnets with -20% RE content, +20% coercivity, and maximum energy product +20%

Independent, resilient and scalable supply of key materials, magnets and components within Europe

Increased sustainability of magnet production with -5% scrap rates, -15% energy consumed and -30% toxicity

Society and stakeholders better equipped for a sustainable green transition in Europe

GREENE CONCEPT

Advanced material models and simulation

Simulations at all scales cover the chemical, mechanical, and magnetic properties of material interfaces in bulk magnets.

A detailed understanding of the local physics and chemistry helps design grain-boundary phases to enhance coercivity.

GREENE CONCEPT

Redesigned rare-earth magnets

Models & Simulation

Optimisation of the grain boundary & Production of magnets with enhanced properties and less critical materials

GREENE GB recreation

$Nd_2Fe_{14}B$ grain

Grain boundary

Novel GB precursors

Short-range exchange coupling

GREENE CONCEPT

A complete value chain

GREENE PARTNERS MAIN ROLES

Coordination

Jožef
Stefan
Institute

Permanent Magnets and Material Science

Jožef
Stefan
Institute

 Hochschule Aalen

 Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

Magnetism at Interfaces

 TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Advanced Nanoscale Analysis

 Universidad
Zaragoza

Sustainability Analysis

Universiteit
Leiden
The Netherlands

Outreach, IP & Strategies for Use of Results

Industrialisation

WIDER IMPACTS

Sustainability and Industrial Leadership

- Developing **scalable advanced materials** to address societal and technological challenges
- Enabling **more recycling of critical / strategic materials**
- **Helping industries** to lower emissions, energy consumption, and negative impacts on people and environment related to current production
- Supporting **digital transformation** of European materials and magnet production
- **Positioning Europe** at the forefront of sustainable innovation

WIDER IMPACTS

Autonomy and Resilience

- **Reducing European dependencies** on third countries for critical / strategic materials
- Encouraging **sector-wide, deep transformations** aligning with EU 2050 goals to become a climate-neutral, circular, and competitive economy
- **Enhancing opportunities** for new markets, products, and services
- Advancing the **competitiveness and leadership** of European industries

WIDER IMPACTS

Scientific and Socioeconomic

- Bringing together various disciplines to **generate high-quality knowledge** in magnetic interfaces on an atomic scale
- Positioning Europe at the **forefront of science and innovation** in the field of rare earth elements, magnetic materials and permanent magnets
- Addressing skill gaps and contributing to **improved employment and social conditions** across Europe
- Fostering **cross-sectoral advancements** by exploring **synergies** with related projects and initiatives

GREENE CONSORTIUM

POSSIBLE SYNERGIES

Sustainability analysis

e.g. baseline LCA, joint non-sensitive/confidential data, environmental impact in REE value chains

'Talking Magnets' (online) seminar series

- with e.g. presentations, discussions, exercises, reading recommendations
- mainly for academic students and junior professionals (research/industry)
- materials and recordings available in Zenodo, if possible

Policy recommendations

GREENE input for e.g. national implementation of CRM Act; obstacles and opportunities for the future of the European REE value chain...

Standardisation

e.g. contribution to WG/TC such as CEN/TC 472 REE and its technical specifications for the labelling of products containing one or more permanent magnets

Joint Communication & Dissemination

- in GREENE channels
- any further opportunity / request: Don't hesitate to get in touch!

Interactive learning tools

- for wider public
- on- and offline
- e.g. infographic, quiz, magnet experiments

Science communication

- Events and activities aimed at the wider public
- Open lab days, public events (open days, girls' day etc.)

European School of Magnetism

- Expert talks
- Student participation

Thank you for your attention!

GREENE Project

greene-project.eu

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